

INFLUENCE OF GRAPHITE SHAPE AND FLAKE ORIENTATION ON FRICTION
AND WEAR CHARACTERISTICS OF Al-50% GRAPHITE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum 2014 alloy-50 vol.% granular and flake graphite particle composites were prepared by pressure infiltration method. Wear tests were carried out using a pin-on-disk wear testing machine. Both the composites containing 50% granular graphite particles or 50% flake graphite particles exhibit a lower friction coefficient and wear rate as compared to the friction coefficient and the wear rate of the base matrix alloy. The shape of the graphite particles (granular or flake) and the orientation of flake graphite in relation to the sliding direction influence the values of the friction coefficient and wear rate in the composites. The composite containing 50 vol.% flake graphite exhibits a higher value of friction coefficient and wear rate as compared to that observed in composites containing 50 vol.% granular graphite. Apparently the narrow dimension of the flake graphite is readily smeared over and rendered ineffective due to plastically deforming aluminum alloy matrix on the tribo-surface during sliding. This phenomenon of flake graphite being smeared over by aluminum is particularly easy when the sliding angle (the angle between the longitudinal direction of flake graphite and the direction of sliding) is high. A sliding angle of around 45 degrees, between the sliding direction and the long direction of flakes, results in minimum values of friction coefficients and wear rates; this may be due to the orientation dependence of the process of squeezing out of graphite from its embedded state to the sliding surface in the form of a film, and the ability of the matrix to flow and cover the graphite particles due to tribo-deformation. Seizure resistance of Al-50% graphite composite, as measured by PV limits, remains at the same level as that of the base alloy at sliding speeds < 3 m/sec.; it appears to exceed that of the base alloy

at sliding speeds > 4 m/sec. The improved friction and wear behavior of composites containing graphite results from the formation of a lubricating film during sliding wear.

KEYWORDS: Friction and Wear; Particulate Composites; Matrix/Aluminum Alloys; Graphite Particle; Film Formation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In our previous studies,⁽¹⁻⁴⁾ lubricating film of graphite formed on the tribo-surface during sliding wear of Al-graphite composites has been examined as a function of graphite content and varying lubrication conditions and sliding parameters. The thickness of the graphite rich solid lubricating film, which presumably reduces the friction coefficient and the wear rate, was measured by means of XPS and AES techniques. The 2-D and 3-D maps of elements on the tribo-surfaces including that of carbon were used to characterize the formation and the distribution of carbon in the graphite film. The transfer of the graphite from the embedded state and its compaction were observed on both the composite surface and the counterface of the steel disk. The mechanism of film formation has been outlined on the basis of observations of deformation of graphite and delamination of the composite. In the present study, Al-graphite composites containing two different types of graphite particles--granular and flake--were prepared by low pressure infiltration technique. The effect of sliding parameters on friction and wear of these composites was investigated. The seizure behavior, the effect of orientation of flake graphite, and the thickness of the lubricating film have been discussed in this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Material Preparation The die used for the process was made of electrode grade hard graphite with 4 in. OD and 2 in. ID. The graphite powders with an average size of 300-500 micron were selected, and the preform was made by putting the powders into the die and tamping the powder bed. The top of the preform was covered by a cloth made of Al₂O₃ fibers.

Aluminum 2014 alloy was chosen as the matrix alloy and was melted in a furnace at a temperature of 760°C before pouring into the die. After pouring, a pressure of 320 psi was employed on the liquid alloy and held for 5 min. The liquid alloy was thus forced to infiltrate into the preform in the die and solidify under pressure, before the casting was ejected out.

2.2. Wear Tests Wear tests were carried out under dry sliding conditions with a typical three pins-on-disk testing machine from FALEX CO. Three pins, (0.63 cm in diameter x 1.5 cm in length) fixed vertically on a round holder equidistant from center with an angular separation of 120 degrees from each other, were sliding against the flat surface of a disk made of 52100 steel with a hardness of HRC55. The normal load, sliding speed and sliding time were variable. The coefficient of friction was obtained by the measurement of torque with an accuracy of ± 0.1 lb-in, and the average weight loss for three samples was obtained by weighing the samples after tests with an accuracy of ≤ 0.0001 gram.

2.3. Measurements of Thickness of the Film Formed SEM, XPS and optical microscopy techniques were used to measure the thickness of the thin lubricating film formed on the tribo-deformed surface of the composites. An Auger/XPS system from V. G. Scientific Ltd. was used for XPS studies, with Mg K_{α} anode (1253.6 eV). Depth profiling was carried out by Ar-ion sputtering at 10 Kv and 0.1 mA/cm². The calibrated sputtering rate was 14 Å/min. The detailed methods used have been reported in Ref. (4).

A Carl Zeiss photomicrographic instrument was used to measure the thickness of the film formed under heavy loads. A reference surface was made by scratching away a small area of the film. Then the measurement was carried out by focusing on the reference and the film surface respectively. The interval of the scale on the fine adjustment of focus corresponds to a 2 μm movement in height from the specimen. Focusing derivation under 400 times magnification is 0.4 μm . An average thickness of the film was taken for each ten measurements.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Friction and Wear Behavior Figures 1(a), (b) and (c) show the photographs of as-cast base 2014 aluminum alloy, base alloy-50 vol.% granular graphite particle composite and the base alloy-50 vol.% flake graphite particle composite respectively. The flake graphite was found oriented along the direction of flow of the molten alloy during infiltration (Fig. 1(c)). The wear tests of the composites containing 50 vol.% flake graphite were carried out in such a manner that the longitudinal direction of the graphite flakes in one pin was parallel to the direction of sliding and the angle between these two directions, called the sliding angle, was 0 degree. In the second pin, the longitudinal direction of the graphite flake was perpendicular to the direction of sliding and the resulting sliding angle was 90 degrees, and in the third pin, the sample was mounted so that the sliding angle was 45 degrees, as shown schematically

in Fig. 2. In this way the effect of orientation of the flake graphite was averaged in the results on friction and wear.

Figures 3 and 4 show the weight loss and coefficient of friction as a function of sliding time for the base alloy and the composites. While the weight losses of two composites due to wear are similar, the base alloy shows an order of magnitude higher weight loss. The coefficient of friction for both the base alloy and the composites remains constant over testing periods exceeding 5 minutes. The coefficient of friction is about 0.44 for the base alloy and that for the composite containing 50 vol.% granular graphite is about 0.25. However, a composite containing 50 vol.% flake graphite shows a higher coefficient of friction of about 0.32 as compared to that in a composite containing the same amount of granular graphite.

The variations of the weight loss and the coefficient of friction as a function of normal load are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 respectively. Again, the weight loss of the base alloy is higher as compared with the weight loss of the composites. The weight loss increases significantly with increasing normal load both for the base alloy and the composite containing 50 vol.% flake graphite. On the other hand, the increase in weight loss with the normal load is lower for the composite containing 50% granular graphite suggesting that the lubricating film formed at the tribo-surface helps to avoid direct metal to metal contact to a large extent. The normal load, up to 33 N, does not significantly affect the coefficient of friction of the composites, as shown in Fig. 6.

The effect of sliding velocity on the weight loss and coefficient of friction is shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. The weight loss increases as the sliding velocity increases for both the base alloy and the composites. The weight loss of the composite containing granular graphite increases at a relatively lower rate with sliding velocity, as compared to the weight loss in the base alloy or composites containing flake graphite, as shown in Fig. 7. The coefficient of friction of both the base alloy and the composites does not change very significantly with an increase in sliding speed.

3.2. Effect on the Temperature Rise at the Sliding Interface The rise in the temperature at the sliding surface measured about 1.5 mm below in the disk counterface is shown in Figs. 9 and 10. The temperature near the interface increases with an increase in the normal load (Fig. 9) or the sliding speed (Fig. 10). The base alloy shows a higher temperature as compared to that observed for the composite containing granular graphite.

The difference in the temperatures observed for the base alloy and the composite increases with increasing normal load or sliding speed. The results from Figs. 9 and 10 suggest that the frictional energy generated by sliding may be relatively low on the surface of the composite as compared with that of the base alloy, due to the formation of the lubricating film on the tribo-deformed surface of the composite.

3.3. Effect of Orientation of Flake Graphite in Composites Containing 50% Graphite

The effect of the orientation of flake graphite on the weight loss and the coefficient of friction is shown in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively. The sliding angle θ in Figs. 11 and 12 refers to the angle between the longitude of flake graphite and the sliding direction (see Fig. 2). The weight loss of the composite is the lowest value when the sliding angle θ is around 45° ; the weight loss increases when the angle is either reduced from 45° to 0° or increased from 45° to 90° . Similarly, the lowest value of coefficient of friction is observed with the sliding angle equal to 45° . The values of the friction coefficient increase when the angle is either decreased from 45° to 0° or when the angle is increased from 45° to 90° .

3.4. P-V Limit

The P-V limit tests were carried out by increasing the normal load in steps at a constant sliding speed and when seizure occurred the test was terminated immediately. Figure 13 shows the P-V limits for both the base alloy and the composite containing granular particles of graphite. Almost the same seizure behavior was observed for both the base alloy and the composite when the sliding speed was lower than 3 m/s. On the other hand, the seizure resistance of the composite containing granular graphite is a little higher than that for the base alloy when the sliding speed exceeded 3 m/s.

3.5. Film Formation and Microstructure

The processes taking place during sliding are more complex for composite materials containing solid lubricants like graphite than those for monolithic metals, because of the lubricating particles embedded in the matrix of the former. Our previous work⁽⁴⁾ has revealed that a thin lubricating film forms on the sliding surface just after a short running distance. The thickness of the film is about 100-200 Å under 10N and 0.1 - 1 m/s in the composites containing 10/50 vol.% of granular graphite. The present studies have revealed that the thickness of the film increases when the composite contains granular graphite in place of flake graphite as shown in Table 1. Figures 14 (a) and (b) show the formation of graphite films on the sliding surface during wear of Al-flake graphite and Al-granular graphite composites respectively.

TABLE 1 THE THICKNESS OF THE FILM FORMED ON THE TRIBO-SURFACE UNDER DIFFERENT SLIDING PARAMETERS

Material	Sliding speed m/s	Normal load N	Thickness of films	Method for measurement	Deviation
Al2014-50% flake graphite	1	44.5	0.8 μm	Carl Zeiss optical	$\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$
Al2014-50% granular graphite	1	115.6	0.78 μm	Carl Zeiss optical	$\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$
Al2014-50% granular graphite	2	222	1.56 μm	Carl Zeiss optical	$\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$

3.6. Discussion In our previous studies, a mechanism of the film formation has been suggested⁽³⁾ which includes: (a) squeezing out of graphite particles from their embedded state due to plastic flow of metal below the sliding surface, and (b) the transfer and compaction of graphite on the composite and counterface. The present study also indicates that almost the entire tribo-surface of the composites is covered by the lubricating film. The sliding process is mostly between the contacting layers of graphite and the debris is generated by delamination when the thickness of the graphite film exceeds the critical value as it has been outlined by N. P. Suh.⁽⁸⁾

Another important phenomenon during sliding in the composites is that of plastic deformation of the aluminum matrix at and below the sliding surface. The plastically deforming aluminum tends to flow on the top of exposed graphite particles and sometimes covers a large fraction. This results in increasing difficulty in squeezing the graphite out of its embedded state, and restricts the supply of graphite on the tribo-surface. This effect potentially reduces the thickness of the film formed on the mating surfaces of the composite or the counterface. Figures 15 (a) and (b) show the microstructures revealing the tribo-deformed layer of the matrix aluminum alloy on the sliding surface of composites containing 50% granular graphite and 50% flake graphite respectively. The flake type of graphite particles appears to be more easily covered by the flow of the tribo-deformed metal layer along its smaller dimension (see Fig. 15b), particularly when the sliding angle is either 0° or 90° . This could be the reason why the composites containing flake graphite exhibit a higher friction and wear rate as compared to composites containing granular graphite which have no small dimension.

The effect of orientation of flake graphite particles comes from a combined influence of the squeezing of graphite and the plastic flow of tribo-deformed matrix resulting in covering of the graphite particles by the deforming matrix. Along the sliding direction parallel to the longitudinal direction of flakes (a sliding angle of 0°), the graphite is hardly squeezed out due to the large dimension of the cavity containing graphite in the direction of sliding. The relative change in dimension due to subsurface shear is very low, creating a smaller squeezing pressure in comparison to that for a cavity of smaller dimension. On the other hand, a sliding direction along the narrow transverse dimension of flake graphite (a sliding angle of 90°) results in covering of the graphite surfaces by plastic flow of the matrix. Kuniya and co-workers⁽⁵⁾ have reported that for Cu-50 vol.% carbon fiber composites, the wear volume for samples with sliding angle of 0 degree is higher than that in samples with 90 degrees of sliding angle. However, a randomly arranged fiber sample exhibits the lowest wear volume.

Another important consequence of the covering of exposed graphite particles by the tribo-deformed matrix during sliding is the larger observed wear in composites containing flake graphite as compared to that in composite containing the same amount of granular graphite. It is difficult for the matrix to cover granular graphite effectively due to the flow of metal mainly in the sliding direction. This results in a larger supply of graphite for film formation on the tribo-surface, and the area fraction of the matrix covered by the graphite film after sliding is larger as compared to that for composites containing flake graphite. Also, the larger the cross section of graphite particles, the more difficult it is for the flow of the matrix to cover it so effectively so as to interfere with the squeezing process of graphite and its supply to the tribo-surface. Thus, the larger the particles of graphite in the composites the better is the wear resistance of the composite as explained by Rohatgi, Ray and Liu⁽⁹⁾ in their review paper on tribological behavior of composites containing graphite.

The formation of the graphitic carbon film also affects the temperature at the interface. The rise of temperature at the interface is lower for the composite compared to that for the base alloy. The low interface temperature for the composite suggests that the film formed on the sliding surface reduces the extent of the metal-metal contact quite effectively.⁽¹⁰⁾ However, the difference in temperature for the base alloy and the composite is not very substantial and it may be due to difficulties in heat transfer in the composite from interface to the subsurface

due to the formation of graphite film having a lower thermal diffusivity as compared to that of the base alloy.

The seizure resistance of materials does not depend on the tribological properties alone but is also a function of their mechanical properties. It has been reported⁽⁷⁾ that the addition of graphite particles into Al base alloys reduces their mechanical properties, especially the tensile strength and ductility. About a 40% reduction in strength has been reported in Al-Si alloy when it contains 20% graphite.⁽⁷⁾ However, improved tribological properties can result in improved seizure resistance, as shown in Fig. 13. The composite, although weak in respect to mechanical properties, can reach almost the same level of seizure resistance as that of the base alloy at a low sliding speed, and it has a better seizure resistance at relatively higher sliding speeds. It is generally believed that formation of the film of graphite during sliding plays an important role in improving the seizure resistance of the composite. The film also reduces the level of normal pressure transmitted through it to the surface of the composite and thereby contributes to the increasing seizure resistance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the present study have led to the following conclusions:

1. Composites containing 50% of either granular or flake graphite particles exhibit reduced friction and wear as compared to the base alloy. The composite having 50% granular graphite has a lower friction and wear rate as compared to the composites containing the same volume percentage of flake graphite.
2. The weight loss of both the aluminum-graphite particle composites and the base alloy increases with an increase of the normal load or the sliding speed or the sliding distance. However, the coefficient of friction for the composites is not significantly affected by the test parameters.
3. The improved friction and wear characteristics of the aluminum-graphite composites has been attributed to the formation of a lubricating graphite film on tribo-surfaces during sliding wear. The thickness of the film increases with an increase in normal load.
4. The narrow dimension of the flake graphite in a composite, when exposed, is easily covered by plastic flow of the aluminum alloy matrix on the tribo-surface during sliding, particularly for a small angle of sliding (the angle between the longitudinal direction of flake graphite and the direction of sliding). A sliding angle of

around 45 degrees results in a minimum value of friction and wear. This effect may have come from the orientation dependence of the process of squeezing out of graphite on the sliding surface and the ability of aluminum alloy matrix to flow and cover the exposed graphite particles under tribo-deformation. These two competing processes respectively help and restrict the supply of graphite on the tribo-surface for the formation of lubricating graphite film.

5. The P-V limits of the Al-50% granular graphite composite is about the same as compared to that of the base alloy at a sliding speed smaller than 3 m/s, and it exceeds that of the base alloy at a sliding speed higher than 4 m/s (about 2.5 MPa higher at a sliding speed of 5 m/s).

5. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Microstructures of the as-cast base alloy (Al2014) a), Al2014-50 v/o granular graphite particle composite b) and Al2014-50 v/o flake graphite particle composite c).

FIGURE 2. A schematic illustration of the sliding angle θ between the longitude of flake graphite and the sliding direction.

FIGURE 3. The weight loss as a function of the sliding time for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 4. The coefficient of friction as a function of the sliding time for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 5. The weight loss as a function of the normal contact load for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 6. The coefficient of friction as a function of the normal contact load for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 7. The weight loss as a function of the sliding velocity for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 8. The coefficient of friction as a function of the sliding velocity for the base alloy and the composites.

FIGURE 9. The temperature measured at 1.5 mm below the sliding interface as a function of the normal contact load for the base alloy and the Al2014-50% granular graphite composite.

FIGURE 10. The temperature measured at 1.5 mm below the sliding interface as a function of the sliding velocity for the base alloy and Al2014-50% granular graphite composite.

FIGURE 11. The weight loss as a function of the sliding angle θ for the base alloy and the Al2014-50% flake graphite composite.

FIGURE 12. The coefficient of friction as a function of the sliding angle θ for the base alloy and the Al2014-50% flake graphite composite.

FIGURE 13. The plots of P-V limits for the base alloy and the Al2014-50% granular graphite composite.

a

b

FIGURE 14. Microstructures of the lubricating film formed on the surface of the composites, a) Al2014-50% granular graphite composite (50 lbs, 2 m/s, 5 min), b) Al2014-50% flake graphite composite (10 lbs, 3 m/s, 5 min).

a

b

FIGURE 15. SEM microstructures of tribo-deformed surfaces of the composites, a) Al2014-50% granular graphite composite, b) Al2014-50% flake graphite composite.